

LUNAR: a tool for setting up process modeling based molecular dynamics simulations

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Outline

Motivation

Background

Methods

Results

Conclusions

Motivation – Lightweight and tailorable properties

“Polymer matrix composites are lighter, stronger, and stiffer than traditional materials—and they can be tailored for specific needs.”

— National Academies

National Academies - High-Performance Structural Fibers for Advanced Polymer Matrix Composites: <https://doi.org/10.17226/11268>.

Nijssen – Composite Materials an introduction

Background - ICME (Integrated computational materials engineering)

Deshpande, 2023: Multiscale Process Modeling of a Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composite for Predicting Residual Stress and Strength

Background - MD simulation

$$\mathbf{r}_A(t + \Delta t) = \mathbf{r}_a(t) + \mathbf{v}_a(\Delta t) + \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{a}_A\right) (\Delta t)^2$$

- \mathbf{F}_A force on an atom
- U_A potential energy
- m_A mass of an atom
- \mathbf{v}_A velocity of an atom
- \mathbf{a}_A acceleration of an atom
- \mathbf{r}_A position of an atom
- Δt timestep

$$\mathbf{F}_A = -\nabla U_A$$

$$\mathbf{a}_A = \frac{\mathbf{F}_A}{m_A}$$

Background - MD simulation

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Background – MD fixed bond force field basics

Bond

$$E = K_2 (r - r_0)^2 + K_3 (r - r_0)^3 + K_4 (r - r_0)^4$$

$$E = D [1 - e^{-\alpha(r - r_0)}]^2$$

Angle

$$E = K_2 (\theta - \theta_0)^2 + K_3 (\theta - \theta_0)^3 + K_4 (\theta - \theta_0)^4$$

Dihedral

$$E = \sum_{n=1}^3 K_n [1 - \cos(n\phi - \phi_n)]$$

Background – MD fixed bond force field basics

Improper

$$E = K \left[\frac{\phi_{ijkl} + \phi_{kjli} + \phi_{ljik}}{3} - \phi_0 \right]^2$$

van der Waals

$$E = \epsilon \left[2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^9 - 3 \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right]$$

Electrostatics

$$E = \frac{Cq_i q_j}{\epsilon r}$$

LUNAR overview

Benchmark systems

Cyanate ester
bisphenol E dicyanate

DGEBF (Qty: 2)
diglycidyl ether bisphenol F

DETDA (Qty: 1)
diethyltoluenediamine

Mix: Randomly place and orientate molecules

cell_builder (random)

cell_builder (amorphous)

cell_builder (grouped)

LAMMPS “*create_atoms*”

Packmol gas

LAMMPS “*replicate*”

Packmol liquid

Mix: Randomly place and orientate molecules

LUNAR/cell_builder.py options

Random (r)

Grouped locally (g)

- Sub cell
- DETDA
- DGEBF
- Simulation cell

Packing results: density

DGEBF/DETDA

Cyanate Ester

Packing results: shrinkage

DGEBF/DETDA

Cyanate Ester

Packing results: free volume

$$ddc_size = 2.1 * \max(\text{system } vdw_radii) + 2 * \text{voxel_size} + 2 * probe_radii$$

$$r_{lo} = r_{particle} - 2 * probe_radii - \text{voxel_size}$$

$$r_{hi} = r_{particle} + 2 * probe_radii + \text{voxel_size}$$

Packing results: free volume

DGEBF/DETDA

Cyanate Ester

Packing results: free volume

Conclusions

- The random packing methods generate the initial simulation cell produces the best model when looking at:
 - Density predictions
 - Post gelation shrinkage
 - FFV
- LUNAR has everything needed for ICME based process modeling using Molecular dynamics
- LUNAR is published at Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling (JCIM)
 - <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.4c00730>
- LUNAR is free to download at:
 - <https://github.com/CMMRLab/LUNAR>

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- Dr. Gregory Odegard
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CMMR Lab

COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICS
& MATERIALS RESEARCH

Motivation – Materials for high heat and extreme environments

Systems:

- Heat shields
- Rocket nozzles
- Braking systems

Carbon-Carbon Composites, G. Savage, 1994

Orion Crew modules: <https://lockheedmartin.com/en-us/news/features/2022/orion-heat-shield.html>

Background: Carbon-carbon composites (PIP method)

Infiltrate/Polymerization

Pyrolysis

Carbon-Carbon Composites, G. Savage, 1994

Comprehensive inorganic chemistry II: From elements to applications. Burlington: Elsevier, 2013

Packing results: potential energy

DGEBF/DETDA

Cyanate Ester

LUNAR performance

DGEBF/DETDA and AroCy L10 Modeling procedure

ChemDraw

LUNAR

LAMMPS

Combinations

5-replicates built

Draw: Initialize start monomer connectivity and positions in ChemDraw

Atom type and apply PCFF-IFF parameters: Using LUNAR

Unify energy coeffs and generate REACTER template: Using LUNAR

Mix: Randomly place and orientate molecules

Densify: 1.18 g/cm³ at 27 C° NVT (experimental liquid density)

Equilibrate: 27 C° 1 atm for 2 ns NPT (liquid density)

Polymerize: 240 C° for 2 ns NVT using REACTER

Equilibrate: 27 C° 1 atm for 2 ns NPT (polymer density)

Gelation behavior

DGEBF/DETDA

AroCy L10

$$\text{Conversion}_{\text{DGEBF/DETDA}} = \frac{\text{reaction 1}_{\text{count}} + \text{reaction 2}_{\text{count}}}{720}$$

$$\text{Conversion}_{\text{L10}} = \frac{\text{reaction 2}_{\text{count}}}{2 * (627/3)}$$

Free volume analysis

$$dd_size = 2.1 * \max(\text{system } R_i^{atom}) + 2 * \text{voxel_size} + 2 * R_j^{probe}$$

$$R_{lo} = P_i^{atom} - 2 * R_j^{probe} - \text{voxel_size}$$

$$R_{hi} = P_i^{atom} + 2 * R_j^{probe} + \text{voxel_size}$$

Free volume convergence and performance

Uncured

Fully cured

Mix: Randomly place and orientate molecules

LUNAR/cell_builder.py options

Random (r)

Grouped locally (g)

MD parameterizing: Atom types

MD parameterizing

Element representation

atom typing

parameterization

$$E_{hc-hc} = \epsilon \left[2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^9 - 3 \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right]$$

$$E_{hc-hc} = \frac{Cq_{hc}q_{hc}}{\epsilon r}$$

$$E_{ho-oh} = K_2 (r - r_0)^2 + K_3 (r - r_0)^3 + K_4 (r - r_0)^4$$

$$E_{hc-c2-hc} = K_2 (\theta - \theta_0)^2 + K_3 (\theta - \theta_0)^3 + K_4 (\theta - \theta_0)^4$$

$$E_{hc-c2-oh-ho} = K_1 [1 - \cos(\varphi - \varphi_n)] + K_2 [1 - \cos(2\varphi - \varphi_n)] + K_3 [1 - \cos(3\varphi - \varphi_n)]$$

MD parameterizing: Transferability

IFF (atom types and parameters are **NOT** transferable to other molecules)

PCFF (atom types and parameters **ARE** transferable to other molecules)

IFF <50 materials
PCFF >100's materials

IFF <0.5% error
PCFF <~10.0% error